

A Proofs and Technical Material

In this Appendix, we provide additional technical details on the required previous results from learning theory and convex analysis, as well as the proofs that have been omitted from the main article.

We first recall some basic notions from learning theory. Let \mathcal{H} be an hypothesis class and $l : Z \times \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a loss function, and assume that, for each $z \in Z$, $l(z, \cdot)$ is convex in its second argument. The main aim of learning theory is, given an hypothesis $h \in \mathcal{H}$, to estimate the expected generalization error of h , that is the quantity $\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}} |L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S(h)|$. Intuitively, if the generalization error of h is small, then the empirical risk of h is a good approximation of its true error: hence, if we observe that h has small empirical risk, then this would provide strong evidence that h will indeed work well on arbitrary data sampled from \mathcal{D} . A fundamental result in learning theory states that the generalization error of any $h \in \mathcal{H}$ can be bounded through the use of the Rademacher complexity, a complexity measure that quantifies the richness of the hypothesis class \mathcal{H} . Formally, the empirical Rademacher complexity $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, S, l)$ of \mathcal{H} w.r.t. a finite sample $S \sim \mathcal{D}^m$ is defined as:

$$\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, S, l) = \mathbb{E}_{\sigma \sim \{-1, 1\}^m} \left[\sup_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \sigma_i \cdot l(h, x_i, y_i) \right], \quad (11)$$

where $\sigma \sim \{-1, 1\}^m$ denotes that σ is drawn from the uniform distribution defined over the set $\{-1, 1\}^m$. The expected Rademacher complexity $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l)$ of \mathcal{H} w.r.t. the data-generating distribution \mathcal{D} is defined as the expected value (w.r.t. \mathcal{D}) of the previously defined empirical Rademacher complexity, that is:

$$\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l) = \mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, S, l). \quad (12)$$

Theorem A.1. *For each hypothesis $h \in \mathcal{H}$, it holds that:*

$$\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} [|L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S(h)|] \leq 2\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l). \quad (13)$$

Furthermore, with probability greater than $1 - \delta$ over the sampling of a finite sample $S \sim \mathcal{D}^m$, if the loss function is B -bounded it holds that:

$$\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} [|L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S(h)|] \leq 2\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, S, l) + 4B \sqrt{\frac{2 \log \frac{2}{\delta}}{2m}}. \quad (14)$$

Proof. See e.g. Theorems 26.3 and 26.5 in [35]. \square

The proof of Theorem A.1, in particular, rests on an another result of separate interest, that we report here.

Proposition A.1 (McDiarmid's Inequality). *Let V be a set and let $f : V^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function. Assume that there exists $c > 0$ s.t. for all $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and for all $x_1, \dots, x_m, x'_i \in V$ it holds that:*

$$|f(x_1, \dots, x_m) - f(x_1, \dots, x_{i-1}, x'_i, x_{i+1}, \dots, x_m)| \leq c.$$

Then, if $X_1, \dots, X_m \sim \mathcal{D}^m$, for some distribution $\mathcal{D} \in \Delta(V)$, with probability greater than $1 - \delta$ it holds that:

$$|f(X_1, \dots, X_m) - \mathbb{E}[f(X_1, \dots, X_m)]| \leq c \sqrt{\frac{m \ln \left(\frac{1}{\delta}\right)}{2}}$$

We, then, provide extended proofs for the results in Sections 2.2 and 2.3. We first provide some results that characterize the collection \mathcal{A} of all generalized aggregation operators as defined in Section 2.2.

Lemma A.1. *Let $l : X \times \Delta(Y) \times \mathcal{H}$ be a loss function satisfying the assumptions given in Section 2: in particular, assume that l is B -bounded. Then, aggregation operators are essentially defined on the domain $\mathbb{I}_B = \{[l, u] \subseteq [0, B] : l \leq u\}$. That is, if A_1, A_2 are two aggregation operators s.t., for each interval $[l, u] \in \mathbb{I}_B$ it holds that $A_1([l, u]) = A_2([l, u])$, then $l_{A_1}^{LP} = l_{A_2}^{LP}$.*

Proof. By assumption, l is convex and L -Lipschitz in its second argument. Therefore, in particular, l is uniformly continuous. As a consequence, for any instance x , hypothesis h and credal set C (which is a convex, closed set and, hence, connected) the set $l(x, C, h) = \{l(x, p, h) : p \in C\}$ is convex and connected. Therefore, $l(x, C, h)$ is a sub-interval of $[0, B]$, since l is B -bounded. Since, for any aggregation operator A , $l_A^{LP}(x, C, h) = A(\{l(x, p, h)\}_{p \in C})$ the result follows. \square

Proposition A.2. *The set of all aggregation operators $\mathcal{A} = \{A | \mathbb{I}_B : A \text{ aggregation operator}\}$, where $A|_{\mathbb{I}_B}$ denotes the restriction of A to \mathbb{I}_B , is compact w.r.t. the sup-norm $|A| = \sup_{[l, u] \in \mathbb{I}_B} A([l, u])$.*

Proof. First of all, as a consequence of Lemma A.1, we note that, in the context of credal learning, the aggregation operators are essentially defined on the collection of closed interval \mathbb{I}_B . Since the pair $(\mathcal{A}, |\cdot|)$ defines a metric space over \mathcal{A} , compactness of \mathcal{A} is equivalent to completeness (i.e., every Cauchy sequence of aggregation operators converges to an aggregation operators) and total boundedness (i.e., for each $\epsilon > 0$ there exists an ϵ -net in \mathcal{A} that covers \mathcal{A}).

For completeness, let A_1, A_2, \dots be a sequence of aggregation operators. Assume that the sequence is Cauchy with respect to the sup norm. Then, for all ϵ , it exists $k(\epsilon)$, s.t. for all $n, m \geq k(\epsilon)$ it holds that $\sup_I |A_n(I) - A_m(I)| \leq \epsilon$. For each $I \in \mathbb{I}_B$, $A_1(I), A_2(I), \dots$ is a Cauchy sequence of real numbers. Indeed, for all $n, m \geq k(\epsilon)$ it holds that $|A_n(I) - A_m(I)| \leq \sup_I |A_n(I) - A_m(I)| \leq \epsilon$. Furthermore, the former sequence is bounded, since $\forall i, 0 \leq \inf I \leq A_i(I) \leq \sup I \leq B$ (since the loss function l is B -bounded). Therefore, since restricted to I the sup norm coincides with the usual metric d on \mathbb{R} and (\mathbb{R}, d) is complete, it follows that the sequence $A_1(I), A_2(I), \dots$ converges to some value I^* . Define a function $A : \mathbb{I}_B \rightarrow [0, B]$ as $A(I) = I^*$, where I^* is defined as above. It is easy to see that, for each $I \in \mathbb{I}_B$ $\inf I \leq A(I) \leq \sup I$. To see that A is monotone, assume that I_1, I_2 are s.t. $I_1 \leq I_2$ in the interval order. Then, for each A_i , it holds that $A_i(I_1) \leq A_i(I_2)$ and monotonicity of A follows from the fact that $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} A_i(I_1) \leq \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} A_i(I_2)$. Thus, \mathcal{A} is complete.

For total boundedness, let $\epsilon > 0$: we need to exhibit an ϵ -net for \mathcal{A} . Let $R = \frac{B}{\epsilon}$. Partition the interval $[0, B]$ into R sub-intervals I_j , each of the form $I_j = [j\epsilon, (j+1)\epsilon]$, for $j \in \{0, \dots, R-1\}$. Each interval $I \in \mathbb{I}_B$ straddles at least one interval I_j : denote with $s(I) = \{j \in \{0, \dots, R-1\} : I \cap I_j \neq \emptyset\}$. For each $k : 2^{\{0, \dots, R-1\}} \times R \rightarrow R$ define the function

$$A_k(I) = \begin{cases} \frac{l\epsilon + (l+1)\epsilon}{2} & \exists A \in \mathcal{A}, A(I) \in [i\epsilon, (i+1)\epsilon] \wedge k(s(I), i) = l \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We note that the collection of all A_k is finite (in particular, the number of A_k is R^{2^R} , which is super-exponential in $\frac{1}{\epsilon}$). Furthermore, while not all functions A_k are aggregation operators, it is easy to see that if the selection function is of the form $k(S, i) = i$, for any $S \in 2^{\{0, \dots, R-1\}}$, then A_k is an aggregation operator. Denote with \mathcal{A}_ϵ the above mentioned family of aggregation operators. Let A be any aggregation operator: we show that there exists k s.t. $\sup_I |A(I) - A_k(I)| \leq \epsilon$. Let I be an arbitrary interval, $s(I)$ the

corresponding set of straddled intervals I_j and let $A(I) \in I_j$: then, we set $k(s(I), l) = l$. By construction, A_k belongs to \mathcal{A}_ϵ . Furthermore, for any $I \in \mathbb{I}_B$, it is easy to see that $|A(I) - A_k(I)| \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2}$. Hence, \mathcal{A}_ϵ is an ϵ -net and \mathcal{A} is totally bounded. The result follows. \square

Theorem 2.1. *Let \mathcal{H} be a convex hypothesis space, l a convex, L -Lipschitz loss function. Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l)$ be the expected Rademacher complexity of \mathcal{H} w.r.t. the true empirical risk L_S . Assume also that \mathcal{D} is $(1 - \eta)$ -calibrated and has degree of ambiguity α . Then, uniformly over $h \in \mathcal{H}$, it jointly holds that $\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} [|L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S^A(h)|]$ can be upper bounded by:*

$$2\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l) + L(\eta + \alpha), \quad (3)$$

$$2\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l) + L\eta + \mathbb{E} \left[|l_A^{IP}(x, C, h) - l_{A^*}^{IP}(x, C, h)| \right], \quad (4)$$

where A^* is defined as

$$A^* = \arg \sup_{A' \text{ aggregation operator}} |l_A^{IP}(x, C, h) - l_{A'}^{IP}(x, C, h)|.$$

Proof of Theorem 2.1. The expected generalization error $\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} [|L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S^A(h)|]$ of h can be decomposed as:

$$\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} \left[|L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S(h) + L_S(h) - L_S^E(h) + L_S^E(h) - L_S^A(h)| \right],$$

by expanding on both the true empirical risk and the annotator-relative empirical risk. The latter formula, through application of the triangle inequality, can be upper bounded by:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} [|L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S(h)|] + \\ & \mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} [|L_S(h) - L_S^E(h)|] + \\ & \mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} [|L_S^E(h) - L_S^A(h)|]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

We then turn to bound each of the three summands above. The first term can be upper bounded, by basic results on Rademacher complexity (see Theorem A.1), by $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l)$.

For the second summand, note that, by the triangle inequality, it holds that:

$$|L_S(h) - L_S^E(h)| \leq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^m |l(x_i, y_i, h) - l(x_i, p_i^*, h)|,$$

which, by additivity of the expected valued can in turn be upper bounded by

$$\mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{D}_X} [|g(\mathcal{D}(x), h(x)) - g(\mathcal{E}(x), h(x))|],$$

where g is the base function for the loss function l . Since l is L -Lipschitz in its second argument, it holds that the previous is upper bounded by $L \cdot \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{D}_X} [d(\mathcal{D}(x), \mathcal{E}(x))]$. Since we assumed that \mathcal{D} is $(1 - \eta)$ -calibrated, it holds that the previous quantity is, by assumption, smaller than $L\eta$.

For the third summand, we first note that it equals

$$\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} \left[\left| \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m g(\mathcal{E}(x_i), h(x_i)) - g(p_{x_i}^*, h(x_i)) \right| \right],$$

where $p_{x_i}^*$ is (one of) the probability measure s.t. $l_A^{IP}(x_i, C, h) = l(x_i, p_{x_i}^*, h)$: such a probability measure is guaranteed to exist, due

to the restriction to compact credal sets. The above can be upper bounded by application of the triangle inequality as:

$$\mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{D}_X} [|g(\mathcal{E}(x), h(x)) - g(p_{x_i}^*, h(x))|].$$

Since, by assumption, g is L -Lipschitz in its second argument, it holds that the previous can be upper bounded by

$$L \cdot \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{D}_X} d(\mathcal{E}(x), p^*) \leq L \cdot \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{D}_X} \text{diam}_d(\mathcal{C}(x)) = L\alpha.$$

Hence, the bound in Eq. (3) holds.

For the bound in Eq. (4), we can use the same decomposition as before, while only changing the analysis for the third summand. We have that $\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} [|L_S^E(h) - L_S^A(h)|]$ can be expressed as:

$$\mathbb{E}_{S \sim \mathcal{D}^m} \left[\left| \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m l(x_i, \mathcal{E}(x_i), h) - l_A^{IP}(x_i, C_i, h) \right| \right],$$

which, by the triangle inequality, can be upper bounded by:

$$\mathbb{E}_{(x, y, C) \sim \mathcal{D}} [|l(x, \mathcal{E}(x), h) - l_A^{IP}(x, C, h)|].$$

. Let A^* be defined as in the Theorem statement. As a consequence of Proposition A.2 A^* exists and is indeed an aggregation operator (as the set \mathcal{A} of all aggregation operators is compact and the function $|l_{A'}^{IP}(x, C, h) - l_A^{IP}(x, C, h)|$ is bounded in $[0, B]$). Hence, the bound in Eq. (4) follows by definition of A^* . \square

Corollary 2.1. *Let $\rho_A(x, C, h) = |l_A^{IP}(x, C, h) - l_{A^*}^{IP}(x, C, h)|$. Assume that there exists η' such that, for all $\eta \leq \eta'$, the data-generating distribution \mathcal{D} is $(1 - \eta)$ -calibrated. Then, under the same conditions of Theorem 2.1, and further assuming that l is B -bounded (see Section 2), with probability greater than $1 - \delta$ over the sampling of $S \sim \mathcal{D}^m$ and uniformly over $h \in \mathcal{H}$, it holds that $L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S^A(h)$ can be jointly upper bounded by:*

$$\Psi_{\delta, l}(\mathcal{H}, S) + L \left(\eta' + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{(x, C) \in S} \text{diam}_d(C) \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\Psi_{\delta, l}(\mathcal{H}, S) + L\eta' + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{(x, C) \in S} \rho_A(x, C, h), \quad (6)$$

where $\Psi_{\delta, l}(\mathcal{H}, S) = 2\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, S, l) + 6B \sqrt{\frac{2 \log(\frac{2}{\delta})}{2m}}$. In particular, let $h = GRM_{l, A}(\mathcal{H}, S)$, and let T be the aggregation operator s.t. $T = \frac{\min + \max}{2}$. Let $h^* = \arg \min_{h' \in \mathcal{H}} L_{\mathcal{D}}(h')$. Then:

- If $A \leq T^9$, then $\rho_A(x, C, h) = \max_{p \in C} l(x, p, h) - l_A^{IP}(x, p, h)$;
- If $A \geq T$ then $\rho_A(x, C, h) = l_A^{IP}(x, p, h) - \min_{p \in C} l(x, p, h)$;

Furthermore, with probability $1 - \delta$, $L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_{\mathcal{D}}(h^*)$ can be upper bounded by:

$$2\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, S, l) + L\eta' + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{(x, C) \in S} \rho_A(x, C, h) + 7B \sqrt{\frac{2 \log(\frac{2}{\delta})}{2m}} \quad (7)$$

Proof of Corollary 2.1. In regard to Eq. (5), we follow the same proof as Theorem 2.1 and obtain Eq. (3). We note that, since l is B -bounded, $\alpha \leq B$. Therefore, we can apply McDiarmid's inequality to both the Rademacher complexity $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l)$ and $\mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{D}_X} \text{diam}_d(\mathcal{C}(x))$ and, with probability greater $1 - \frac{\delta}{2}$, it holds that:

⁹ Let $A_1, A_2 \in \mathcal{A}$. $A_1 \leq A_2$ if $A_1(I) \leq A_2(I) \forall I \in \mathbb{I}_B$.

$$\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, m, l) \leq \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{H}, S, l) + 2B\sqrt{2\log\frac{2}{\delta}2m},$$

and

$$\mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{D}_X} \text{diam}_d(\mathcal{C}(x)) \leq \frac{1}{m} \sum_{(x,C) \in S} \text{diam}_d(C) + 2B\sqrt{2\log\frac{2}{\delta}2m}.$$

Therefore, by applying the union bound, Eq. (5) holds. The result for Eq. (6) can be obtained following the same line of reasoning, by noting that ρ_A is B -bounded (since l is B -bounded), and hence we can apply the McDiarmid's inequality to recover the bound in the Theorem statement.

As for the statement on ρ_A , we note that the value of ρ_A directly stems from its definition and the monotonicity of A . Indeed, assume first that $A \leq T$. Let x, C and p^A, p^T, p_*, p^* be distributions in C s.t. $l_A^{IP}(x, C, h) = l(x, p^A, h)$, $l_T^{IP}(x, C, h) = l(x, p^T, h)$, $l_{\min}^{IP}(x, C, h) = l(x, p_*, h)$, $l_{\max}^{IP}(x, C, h) = l(x, p^*, h)$. It is easy to see that $l(x, p^A, h) \leq l(x, p^T, h) \leq \frac{l(x, p_*, h) + l(x, p^*, h)}{2}$ and the statement follows. The proof for the case $A \geq T$ is analogous.

Finally, the bound in Eq. (7) derives from Eq. (6) by noting that $L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_{\mathcal{D}}(h^*) = L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S^A(h) + L_S^A(h) - L_S^A(h^*) + L_S^A(h^*) - L_{\mathcal{D}}(h^*) \leq |L_{\mathcal{D}}(h) - L_S^A(h)| + |L_S^A(h^*) - L_{\mathcal{D}}(h^*)|$. The second term can be upper bounded, with probability $1 - \frac{\delta}{2}$, by applying Hoeffding's inequality as:

$$B\sqrt{\frac{2\log\frac{2}{\delta}}{2m}},$$

while the first term can be upper bounded as shown previously for Eq. (6). \square

Theorem 2.2. Let $\rho_A(x, C, h)$ and T be defined as in Corollary 2.1. Let $U(h, A) = L_S^A(h) + \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{(x,C) \in S} \rho_A(x, C, h)$. Let $\mathcal{A}_T = \{A \text{ aggregation operator} \mid A = T \vee A \geq T \vee A \leq T\}$. Then $T \in \arg \min_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \rho_A(x, C, h)$ and $U(h, T) = \frac{L_S^{\min}(h) + L_S^{\max}(h)}{2}$. Furthermore:

- If $A \leq T$, then $U(h, A) = L_S^{\max}(h) \geq U(h, T)$;
- If $A > T$, then $U(h, A) = 2L_S^A(h) - L_S^{\min}(h) \geq L_S^{\max}(h) \geq U(h, T)$.

Thus, $T \in \arg \min_{A \in \mathcal{A}} U(h, A)$.

Proof of Theorem 2.2. First, we note that as a consequence of our assumptions the aggregation operator T makes sense, in the sense that, for each instance (x, C) , it exists a probability distribution $p_x^T \in C$ s.t. $l_T^{IP}(x, C, h) = l(x, p_x^T, h)$. Then, as a consequence of Corollary 2.1, we know that if $A \in \mathcal{A}_T$, it either holds that $\rho_A(x, C, h) = \max_{p \in C} l(x, p, h) - l_A^{IP}(x, p, h)$, if $A \leq T$; or $\rho_A(x, C, h) = l_A^{IP}(x, p, h) - \min_{p \in C} l(x, p, h)$, if $A \geq T$. Thus, a way to minimize $\rho_A(x, C, h)$ is to select an aggregation operator A s.t. $\max_{p \in C} l(x, p, h) - l_A^{IP}(x, p, h) = l_A^{IP}(x, p, h) - \min_{p \in C} l(x, p, h)$. This holds, in particular, when $A = T$. For the second statement, it suffices to evaluate $U(h, A)$ for the different cases that can arise from aggregation operators in \mathcal{A}_T . \square

Theorem 2.3. Let \mathcal{H} be a convex subset of a vector-valued Reproducing Hilbert Kernel Space (RKHS). Let l be a loss function satisfying the assumptions stated in Section 2. Assume that $\max_{h \in \mathcal{H}} \|h\| \leq$

B . Then, for any $S \sim \mathcal{D}^m$, if Algorithm 1 is executed for T steps, returning hypothesis $h = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i K_{\mathcal{H}}(\cdot, x_i)$, it holds that, with probability greater than $1 - \delta$ over the randomization in the Algorithm:

$$L_S^{\min}(h) - L_S^A(\text{GRM}_{l, \min}(\mathcal{H}, S)) \leq \frac{4B^2L}{\delta\sqrt{T}}. \quad (9)$$

Thus, if T_G denotes the time required to evaluate a subgradient of l , and $T_P(|Y|)$ denotes the time required to compute the d -projection at line 8 of Algorithm 1, then the ORM problem can be ϵ -approximated (with probability of error smaller than δ) within time complexity $O\left(\frac{B^4L^2}{\delta^2\epsilon^2} [T_G + T_P(|Y|)]\right)$. In particular, if, with probability 1 over $(x, y, C) \sim \mathcal{D}$ it holds that C is a probability interval (resp., a possibility distribution, a comparative probability, a linear credal set), then the ORM problem can be ϵ -approximated (with probability of error smaller than δ) within time complexity $O\left(\text{poly}\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon}, \frac{1}{\delta}, |Y|\right)\right)$.

Proof of Theorem 2.3. We note that, since \mathcal{H} is (convex subset of) a RKHS, and l is convex in its second and third arguments, it holds, by the Representer theorem, that $\text{GRM}_{l, \min}(\mathcal{H}, S) = \sum_{i=1}^{|S|} \alpha_i K_{\mathcal{H}}(\cdot, x_i)$, for some vector $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{|S|}$. Since the base function of l, g , is L -Lipschitz in its first and second argument, and \mathcal{H} is B -bounded, l is LB -Lipschitz in its last argument (i.e., in h). Algorithm 1 is simply (block) stochastic coordinate descent, where the two block of coordinates α and P represent, respectively, the coefficients in the kernel expansion of the hypothesis h to be learned, and the probability distributions over Y s.t. $P[i, \cdot] = \arg \min_{p \in C_i} l(x, p, h)$. Since l is convex in its second and third arguments, by the convergence properties of stochastic coordinate descent (see, e.g. Theorem 6.1 in [41] and Theorem 14.8 in [35]), it holds that, if one executes Algorithm 1 for T steps:

$$\mathbb{E}[L_S^{\min}(h)] - L_S^A(\text{GRM}_{l, \min}(\mathcal{H}, S)) \leq \frac{4B^2L}{\sqrt{T}},$$

where the expectation is on the randomization in Algorithm 1. Then, the first statement of the result follows by Markov's inequality. For the second statement, this can be simply be obtained by setting the right-hand side of Eq. (9) equal to ϵ and then solving for T . Finally, the last statement can be directly obtained by noting that the projection problem for the classes of credal sets specified in the Theorem statement can be solved in polynomial time through interior point methods. Indeed, noting that the class of linear credal sets is the larger among the ones considered in the previous statement, one can apply any polynomial-time algorithm (e.g. the barrier method, see [4], Section 11.3.1) for the minimization of a bounded, Lipschitz convex function over a linear polytope to perform the projection step in Algorithm 1. \square

Corollary A.1. Let $\mathcal{D} \in \Delta(X \times Y \times [0, 1]^Y)$ be s.t., with probability 1 over $(x, y, \pi) \sim \mathcal{D}$ it holds that $\pi(y) > 0$ and $\exists y' \in Y, \pi(y') = 1$ (i.e., \mathcal{D} defines a learning from fuzzy labels problem). Let $\phi: [0, 1]^Y \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ be defined as

$$\phi(A) = \{p \in \Delta(Y) : 1 - \max_{y' \neq y} \pi(y') \leq p(y) \leq \pi(y)\}.$$

Let $\phi(\mathcal{D}) \in \Delta(X \times Y \times \mathcal{C}(Y))$ be the distribution defined as $\phi(\mathcal{D})(x, y, C) = \mathcal{D}(x, y, \phi^{-1}(C))$. Let $S = \{(x_1, A_1), \dots, (x_m, y_m)\}$ be a finite sample drawn i.i.d from \mathcal{D} and $\phi(S) = \{(x_i, \phi(A_i))\}_{i=1}^m$. Let l be a loss function, \mathcal{H} an hypothesis

class, L_S^F be defined as

$$L_S^F = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \int_0^1 \min_{y \in \{y' \in A: \pi_i(y') \geq \alpha\}} l(x, \delta_y, h) d\alpha,$$

and $L_\phi(S)^{\min}$ be defined as in Section 2. Then, unless $P = NP$, minimizing L_S^F is computationally harder than minimizing $L_{\phi(S)}^{\min}$.

Furthermore, the above result holds also if $\forall y \in Y, \pi(y) \in \{0, 1\}$, with probability 1 over $(x, y, \pi) \sim \mathcal{D}$.

Proof. The problem of minimizing L_S^F is the same as the problem of solving ORM in learning from fuzzy labels using the algorithmic approach described in [16]: this problem is in general known to be NP-HARD [6], as it is a non-convex, non-smooth optimization problem. By contrast, $L_{\phi(S)}^{\min}$ can be minimized using Algorithm 2, as it is easy to see that the above mentioned problem is equivalent to ORM for credal learning: in particular, Theorem 2.3 shows that it can be solved in polynomial time whenever the credal sets are constrained to be possibility distributions.

For the second statement, the result follows by noting that the problem of minimizing L_S^F is, in this case, equivalent to solving ORM in superset learning: as for the general case of learning from fuzzy labels, this problem is generally known to be NP-HARD [16]. \square

Theorem 2.4. *Let $\mathcal{H}, l, K_{\mathcal{H}}$ be as in Theorem 2.3. Then, for any $S \sim \mathcal{D}^m$, if Algorithm 1 is executed for T steps, returning hypothesis $h = \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i K_{\mathcal{H}}(\cdot, x_i)$, it holds that, with probability greater than $1 - \delta$ over the randomization in the Algorithm:*

$$L_S^{\max}(h) - L_S^{\max}(GRM_{l, \max}(\mathcal{H}, S)) \leq \frac{BL}{\delta \sqrt{T}}. \quad (10)$$

In particular, the problem of solving PRM cannot be solved efficiently for arbitrary credal sets.

Proof of Theorem 2.4. For the proof of the first statement, note that, since l is convex in its second and third arguments and, with probability 1 over $(x, y, C) \sim \mathcal{D}$, C is convex and, it holds that, for any fixed $h \in \mathcal{H}$, the probability distribution $p^* \in C$ for which $l(x, p^*, h) = l_{\max}^{IP}(x, C, h)$ is one of the extremes of C . Indeed, assume the contrary and there exists p^* that satisfies the above condition and $\exists p_1, p_2 \in C$, with $p_1 \neq p_2$ and $p^* = \lambda p_1 + (1 - \lambda)p_2$, for some $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. Then, by convexity of l , it holds that $l(x, p^*, h) \leq \lambda l(x, p_1, h) + (1 - \lambda)l(x, p_2, h) \leq \max\{l(x, p_1, h), l(x, p_2, h)\}$, thus l is maximized over the entire face of C defined by p_1, p_2 . By Krein-Milman theorem [32], this face of C contains at least one extreme, which is also an extreme of C . Therefore, step 7 and 8 of Algorithm 2 compute the exact value of $l_{\max}^{IP}(x, C, h)$, for any fixed h . The result then follows by the convergence of SGD (see, e.g., Theorem 14.8 in [35]). \square

Corollary A.2. *Let T_G the time required to evaluate a subgradient of l . Then, for Algorithm 2, the following hold:*

- If \mathcal{D} defines a superset learning problem (see Section 2), then Algorithm 2 ϵ -approximates PRM (with probability of error smaller than δ) within time complexity $O\left(\frac{B^2 L}{\delta^2 \epsilon^2} [T_G + |S||Y|]\right)$;
- If, with probability 1 over $(x, y, C) \sim \mathcal{D}$, C is a probability interval (resp. possibility distribution) and $Y \in O(\log(|S|))$, then Algorithm 2 ϵ -approximates PRM (with probability of error smaller than δ) within time complexity $O\left(\frac{B^2 L}{\delta^2 \epsilon^2} [T_G + |S||Y|]\right)$;

- If, with probability 1 over $(x, y, C) \sim \mathcal{D}$, C is a comparative probability assessment, and $Y \in O(\log(|S|))$, then Algorithm 2 ϵ -approximates PRM (with probability of error smaller than δ) within time complexity $O\left(\frac{B^2 L}{\delta^2 \epsilon^2} [T_G + |S||Y|^2]\right)$;
- If, with probability 1 over $(x, y, C) \sim \mathcal{D}$, C is a linear credal set, and $Y \in O(\log(|S|))$, then Algorithm 2 ϵ -approximates PRM (with probability of error smaller than δ) within time complexity $O\left(\text{poly}\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon}, \frac{1}{\delta}, |S||Y|\right)\right)$.

Proof. For the case of superset learning, it is easy to see that any credal set in the form $A = \{\sum_i w_i p_{y_i} : w_i \in [0, 1], \sum_i w_i = 1\}$, for $y_1, \dots, y_k \in Y$ s.t. $y \in \{y_1, \dots, y_k\}$, has at most $|Y|$ extreme points. In particular the extreme points of A , defined as above, are

$$\text{the Dirac distributions } \delta_{y_i}(y) = \begin{cases} 1 & y = y_i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

For the other statements, we note that probability intervals [31], possibility distributions [28], comparative probability assessments [29], as well as linear credal sets [3], all have at most $2^{|Y|}$ extreme points: by assumption, this is upper bounded by $|S|^c$, for some $c \in \mathbb{N}$. The extreme points of a probability interval (resp., possibility distribution) can be enumerated by means of a linear delay (in $|Y|$) algorithm [31], similarly the extreme points for a comparative probability assessment can be enumerate by means of a quadratic delay (in $|Y|$) algorithm [29]. Finally, the extreme points of a linear credal set can be enumerated by the simplex method, which is a polynomial (in $|Y|$ and k , the number of inequalities that define the linear credal set) delay algorithm [33]. The result follows. \square